

A Prospective Study on the Application of MOOC in Teacher Professional Development

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Abstract

Teacher professional development is the process-oriented technique. It is not limited to teaching and learning process and is constantly strengthening professional attainment, broadening academic knowledge, enhancing the professional skills, and improving teaching ability. Theories have been shifted where learning process has become more interactive and effective and has thoroughly shifted learning to teaching only because of educational technology. With the reform of learning science and the development of Information and Communication Technology (ICT), the primitive mode of teacher professional development is confronted with challenge, if educational technology is limited to audio-visual aids, mechanical and electronic gadgets the scope of educational technology becomes limited and the new emerging MOOC system provides a new way for teacher professional development. The MOOC system is an essential tool for teacher professional development because of teacher's professional development, characteristics, teacher's needs, and the cost of imbedding the skills. Studies are still at the trial stage that is at an initial point and we need to carry on emphatically analysis on the policy, quality and value of the application of MOOC to teacher professional development so that teacher should gain maximum advantage which is the ultimate goal for their development. Coursera and many other ed tech platforms carried out different assignments and with lots of research they have come out with unique LMS which is benefitable universally in the teaching field. Presently, the use of MOOC system to teacher professional development is still at the inception stage of where experiments are going on and new theories are building with advancement knowledge probably that is the need of the hour, so as to deal with various potential obstacles to overcome different difficulties and solve possible problems in near foreseen future.

Keywords: Educational technology, MOOC, instructional aids, Web 2.0.

Introduction-

A **Massive Open Online Courses** is a web-based distance mode learning program which is mostly efficient for the disadvantaged group. It would typically involve examining their effectiveness, accessibility, and impact on learners and education systems. Mostly they are available as a free online resource for anyone to enrol. MOOCs provide an affordable and flexible way with a customised leaning management system (LMS) to learn new skills, advance your career and deliver quality educational experiences at scale.

Technology is a scientific way for developing new techniques. It is a systematic way of evolving and applying these techniques. Technology can also be called a methodology for designing new techniques. There are millions of users who are using MOOC platform as it is vulnerably useful which includes - Career development, Flexible career options, college preparations, additional learning options, lifelong learning, corporate e-Learning and more.

MOOCs have dramatically changed the way the world for everyone and not only the students are favoured with this modern science but educators are exposed too, as the development of learning

science and the evolution of information and communication technology provides diverse methods for teacher's professional development. The application of remote educational system in teacher is an ongoing process and MOOC has played an eminent role in developing their skill. Educational technology is an instrument of work engaging in human activities and involving in constructive activities. If the course of history is to be surveyed correctly then only the dark imminence of the unknown future is to be in any way penetrated.

Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) have triggered much discussion, particularly on the way in which they provide learning opportunities of high quality to numerous learners available on the internet around the globe at no cost or at a nominal charge, as long as they have open access to computer-based devices that can be connected via the internet to the MOOCs. Currently available statistics reveal a significant number of MOOCs that are on offer in virtually every discipline - humanities, social science, natural science, engineering, medicine, education, and other professional training, and so forth. There are MOOCs that are of very high quality and of very low quality. There are MOOCs that are paid for and that are offered for free. There are MOOCs that attract thousands or more learners or very few, if at all. Not all the MOOCs achieve their intended targets, although most who enrol are learners who are mature in age, educated, and already in employment. These observations are generally perceived as forewarning and, at the same time, alert to what is to be expected in a MOOC.

Advantages of using MOOC Platform over Traditional Method -

MOOC is easy and flexible to use and can be operated from anywhere. The only requirement is that of internet connectivity and a computer. Teachers can have flexible learning hours, and can study and gain knowledge according to their convenience.

MOOCs enable the learner to choose from wide variety of options available. Additionally, it gives a great help in achieving cognitive objectives. Teachers can choose the subject area in which they want to update and upgrade their knowledge and can choose from a pool of topics offered.

MOOC is almost free, except the certification for which there is a nominal fee. The educational institutions would also be relieved from the financial burden of providing professional development training programs for teaching purpose at affordable cost.

Individual differences can be controlled through this technology because students can learn according to their own pace. The correct response of the students can be confirmed easily with the help of online discussion and can be reinforced accordingly.

Technology is an opium of intellectuals and for guarding against super egoism, the responsible technology is much more required.

MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) offer several advantages over traditional learning methods. Here are some key benefits:

1. **Accessibility:** MOOCs can be accessed anywhere with an internet connection, breaking geographical barriers.
2. **Flexibility:** Learners can study at their own pace, choosing when and where to engage with course materials.
3. **Diverse Course Offerings:** MOOCs cover a wide range of subjects and specializations, allowing learners to explore interests beyond their formal education.
4. **Cost-Effective:** Many MOOCs are free or low-cost compared to traditional courses, making education more affordable.
5. **Self-Paced Learning:** Students can tailor their learning experience to their own needs, revisiting material as needed.
6. **Resource-Rich:** MOOCs often include a variety of multimedia resources, interactive forums, and collaborative projects.
7. **Networking Opportunities:** Learners can connect with peers and instructors from around the globe, enhancing their professional network.
8. **Skill Enhancement:** One of the key role of MOOC is it help the teachers to enhance their skills according to the latest trend in turn making them more aware about the needs of changing society.

9. **No Prerequisites:** Many MOOCs do not require prior qualifications, allowing anyone to learn new skills or knowledge.
10. **Continuous Learning:** MOOCs provide options for ongoing education, enabling lifelong learning without the constraints of a traditional schedule.

These advantages make MOOCs an appealing alternative for learners seeking flexibility, accessibility, and a wide range of learning opportunities.

Thus, it can be said MOOC is an applied or practical study which aims at maximum educational effect by controlling such relevant facts as educational purposes, educational contents teaching material, methods, educational environment, conduct of students, behaviour of instructors and interrelation between student and instructors.

MOOCs Platform in India:

SWAYAM	https://swayam.gov.in/
NPTEL	https://nptel.ac.in/
MooKIT	https://www.mookit.in/
IIT Bombay x	https://iitbombayx.in/
Shikshit India	https://www.shikshitbharat.com/
Vskills	https://www.vskills.in/certification/
U18	https://online.uni-mysore.in/
Apna course	https://www.apnacourse.com/
UpGrad	https://www.upgrad.com/
Edukart Open	https://www.educart.co/
Learn Vern	https://www.learnvern.com/
Digital Vidya	https://www.digitalvidya.com/

Chief Objectives of Moocs in Teachers' Professional Development

As far as the MOOCs are concerned, it is absolutely e- revolutionized by educational technology, MOOC has demonstrated its potential in teacher professional development. MOOC is promising for its MOOC framework, connectivism base and scientific evaluation and certifications. However, the quality and variety of course resources still cannot meet the demand of teacher professional development. The insufficient fund adversely triggered the quality and quantity of MOOC course resources, which could hardly meet the needs of teacher's overall professional development. Till 2014, there are 58 courses related to teacher professional development, according to Education Commission (1964-66) has recommended that the fundamental objectives in the curriculum should be improved so that teachers can be prepared for various responsibilities towards education. The language barrier affects the learning results and teachers learning interest which is one of the barriers affecting the skills. The present online teacher education courses are too general, and cannot meet the needs of teachers with different characteristics, different disciplines, or different districts, which compromises their educational efficiency and influence.

Following are the important objectives that we aim to expand MOOC in order to enhance the skills:

- * The flexible environment of MOOC has changed the stereotype way of understanding things and made the classroom teaching more interactive.
- * The policies from the government provides essential aids, and the contributions from the MOOC users, especially instructors, will guarantee the quality of MOOC in the geographical.
- * MOOC provides a new platform for teachers to demonstrate, maintain, and evaluate their career proficiency.
- * MOOC provides teachers to reach to the disadvantaged group of the country making nation more accessible.
- * With learning platforms, it is easy for the teachers to interact with the parents/guardian without hassle.

- * Innovative activities that is interactive gathering is so easy if teachers are engaging students through MOOC platform and is one of the important objectives.
- * Cultural collaboration, engaging with diverse knowledge systems, and preparing students to thrive in an increasingly interconnected and interdependent world is so easy with the help of MOOC

There are Six Professional Learning Goals for Teachers -

- I. Master new technologies
- II. Lear new teaching technique and theories
- III. Improve your classroom presentation
- IV. Increase student engagement
- V. Learn classroom management technique
- VI. Meet state license requirement

Teachers' Professional Smart Goal to be Achieve by Mooc

- Continuing Education
- Participation in professional organizations
- Research
- Improve job performance
- Increased duties and responsibilities
- Skill based training
- Job assignments
- Approaches to professional development
- Developmental Relationship

Impact of Moocs on Teacher Education -

Massive Open Online Courses have the potential to empower learner by enhancing access to education and not only helping students but triggering the growth of teacher in many ways. "No more stereotype

teaching is prevalent in this digital era and there it is so essential for teacher to upskill in order to keep the standards of education high”.

1. **Diversity:** Globalization has led to increased cultural diversity in higher education institutions. Students from all around the world have the opportunity to study and collaborate, leading to a more culturally rich learning environment. MOOCs provide access to quality education for people all over the world, regardless of their location or socioeconomic status.
2. **Internationalization:** MOOCs are available at any time and from any location, and learners can choose their own pace. Thus, needs of MOOCs are increasingly engaging in international partnerships and collaborations. This includes student exchange programs, joint research initiatives, and international campus branches, offering students a more global perspective. MOOCs can help students demonstrate their competency in a particular subject or skill.
3. **Curriculum:** MOOCs has influenced the content of academic curriculum, with a greater emphasis on international issues, cross-cultural understanding, and global perspectives in various disciplines. Many MOOCs include real-world projects and assignments that help students gain practical experience. It provides a platform for learners to interact with each other in a one-on-one way with the instructors.
4. **Upskilling:** MOOCs has facilitated the exchange of knowledge and resources through technological advancements. Online courses, digital libraries, and virtual collaborations have become more accessible, connecting students and educators globally. Thus, can help unemployed people develop skills that can help them find employment, and can also help employees receive free training.
5. **Economic Impact:** Globalization has influenced the funding and financial aspects of higher education, with international students contributing to the economic base of universities and colleges. It can improve the quality of learning by using technology-based teaching tools.
6. **Workforce Preparation:** Higher education institutions are adapting their programs to prepare students for a globalized workforce, equipping them with the talents, skills and knowledge which is ultimately require to succeed in diverse international environments.
7. **Research and Innovation:** Globalization has fostered greater cross-border collaboration in research and innovation, leading to advancements in various fields of study and expanding opportunities for academic and scientific exchange. MOOCs have democratized learning by making high-quality education accessible to more people.
8. **Competition and Rankings:** Globalization has intensified competition among higher education institutions, leading to a focus on international rankings, reputation, and global competitiveness.
9. **Mobility:** Globalization has increased student and faculty mobility, with more opportunities for studying abroad, participating in international conferences, and pursuing research in global contexts.
10. **Policy and Governance:** MOOCs has influenced higher education policies and governance structures, prompting institutions and governments to adapt to the changing landscape of international education. It contributes to the continuous education of various social groups.

The impact of MOOCs on teacher education continues to evolve, presenting both opportunities and challenges for institutions, educators, and students as they navigate the complexities of a globalized academic environment.

1. **Student Mobility:** Students studying abroad or participating in exchange programs to gain international experience.
2. **Curriculum Internationalization:** Incorporating global perspectives, diverse cultures, and international issues into the curriculum.
3. **Research Collaboration:** Academic institutions collaborating on research projects across borders, leading to shared knowledge and innovations.
4. **Branch Campuses:** Universities establishing campuses in different countries to expand their reach and offer education globally.

5. **Online Education:** Providing online courses and programs accessible to students worldwide, transcending geographical boundaries.
6. **Cultural Exchange Programs:** Initiatives promoting cultural understanding and collaboration among students and faculty from different nations.
7. **International Partnerships:** Collaborations between universities from different countries for joint programs, research, and faculty exchanges.
8. **Language Learning:** Encouraging the learning of multiple languages to facilitate communication and understanding in a global context.
9. **Global Rankings:** Universities competing globally for rankings, leading to increased international visibility and reputation.
10. **E-Learning Platforms:** Utilizing digital platforms for education delivery, enabling wider access and interaction among students worldwide.

These types of globalization in higher education contribute to a more interconnected, diverse, and dynamic academic landscape.

Challenges Faced by Moocs in India -

MOOC being a new medium of education has yet to be testing on a global level. There are still countries like India which have yet to embrace this modern constructivist learning tool fully, despite being more accessible than ever before. With several research studies proving its efficacy in modern education settings, it has yet to be embraced effectively in our education system. Most guardians would rather hire a private tutor over MOOC as it may have a point of individual difference but still it does not have a personal touch. There are so many MOOC platforms available today online that provide degrees and certification of completion but firstly it's not free of cost and secondly, in terms of recognition and prestige they fail in comparison to authentic degrees and awards from established universities and education boards. Our approach should be collaboration, not competition. We have pointed out the poor quality of the online courses offered, however the extremely poor retention rate, decline in the quality of pedagogy, problems with medium of instruction to name a few, that will take a lot of collective effort from the state and educational institutions providers should try to integrate with universities and become official partners in providing supplementary or complimentary learning resources. Similarly, schoolteachers and college lecturers should encourage students to enrol in online courses to enhance their knowledge and learning capabilities. The formula for a university's success applies to MOOC too. To grow and expand, international collaboration is essential for the various MOOC platforms to develop. Moreover, some of the EdTech platforms which are presently available in India are owned by foreign companies. There must be arrangement to confront with the needs and challenges of India. Constructivist pedagogy relies on immediate feedback as it works on activities and back & forth communication which requires a stable internet connection. For MOOC to be successful, the government bodies need to take initiative in the expansion and lessening the barrier where people can be more technically sound.

Some of the points highlight the challenges:

1. **Cultural Integration:**
Cultural differences among students and faculty can lead to misunderstandings and conflicts, requiring strategies for effective communication and collaboration.
2. **Language Barriers:**
Students from diverse linguistic backgrounds may face challenges in studying in a different language, necessitating language support services.
3. **Diversity Management:**
Managing a diverse student body with varying cultural norms and academic backgrounds demands inclusive policies and support systems.
4. **Academic Standards Alignment:**
Ensuring alignment of academic standards across institutions globally is essential for maintaining the quality and recognition of degrees.

5. **Funding Disparities:**

Disparities in funding among institutions can impact their ability to participate in international collaborations and provide quality education.

Role of Government in Promoting Moocs for Teacher's Professional Growth -

Governments play a crucial role in promoting MOOCs for teacher professional growth through various initiatives and support mechanisms. Here are some key roles they can fulfil:

1. **Funding and Grants:** Providing financial support for developing quality MOOC content specifically for educators, as well as funding scholarships for teachers to enrol in these courses.
2. **Collaboration with Institutions:** Partnering with universities and educational organizations to create and offer high-quality MOOCs tailored for teacher development.
3. **Awareness Campaigns:** Running campaigns to inform teachers about the availability and benefits of MOOCs, encouraging them to engage in professional development.
4. **Infrastructure Development:** Investing in technological infrastructure to ensure teachers have reliable internet access and digital resources necessary to participate in online courses.
5. **Incentives for Participation:** Offering rewards, certification, or professional development credits for teachers who complete relevant MOOCs, motivating them to pursue further education.
6. **Integration into Professional Standards:** Helping incorporate MOOC participation into teacher training and continuing education requirements, validating the value of online learning.
7. **Quality Assurance:** Establishing standards and evaluation criteria for MOOCs to ensure the content is pedagogically sound and effective for teacher professional growth.
8. **Support Systems:** Creating platforms for mentorship, peer support, and discussion forums, facilitating community building among educators participating in MOOCs.
9. **Research and Feedback:** Conducting research on the impact of MOOCs on teacher performance and professional growth, using findings to improve course offerings.
10. **Promotion of Lifelong Learning:** Advocating for a culture of lifelong learning within the education sector, emphasizing the importance of continuous professional development through innovative methods like MOOCs.

By focusing on these roles, governments can significantly enhance the effectiveness and reach of MOOCs, thereby improving the professional growth opportunities available to teachers.

Conclusion-

In nutshell, the application of MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) in teacher professional development has proven to be a transformative approach, providing educators with flexible, accessible learning opportunities. Here's a concise conclusion:

MOOCs enhance teacher professional development by offering a wide range of subjects, facilitating lifelong learning, and connecting educators globally. They promote self-paced learning, allowing teachers to tailor their education to individual needs and schedules. Furthermore, the diverse formats – videos, discussions, and assessments – cater to various learning styles, improving engagement and retention.

Collaboration and networking opportunities through forums and peer interactions foster a sense of community, enabling knowledge sharing and support. However, challenges such as variable course quality, digital literacy, and motivation levels must be addressed to maximize their benefits.

In summary, when thoughtfully integrated into professional development programs, MOOCs can significantly enrich teachers' skills, drive innovation in education, and ultimately enhance student outcomes.

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